

LEADCOR

LEADERSHIP DEVELOPMENT FOR OCCUPATIONAL
STRESS REDUCTION IN CORRECTIONAL SETTINGS

LEADCOR User's Manual

Leadership Competencies in Correctional Settings

Module III - Leadership Competencies

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LEADCOR - Leadership development for occupational stress reduction in correctional setting

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Project's website - <https://www.leadership-corrections.org/>

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Module III - Leadership Competencies

Overview of the Module III

Welcome to the **Module III** about **Leadership Competencies**! This Module is divided into **5 Chapters**:

- In Chapter “**Emotional Intelligence**”, we will focus on the **subchapter**:
 - Five Elements of Emotional Intelligence;

- In Chapter “**What is Communication?**”, we will focus on the **subchapters**:
 - Verbal and Nonverbal Communication;
 - Clearly Communication.

- **In Chapter “How to Solve Conflicts?”**, we will focus on the **subchapters**:
 - Defining Conflict;
 - Conflict Management;
 - Enabling Change after the Conflict.

- **In Chapter “How important is Motivation?”**, we will focus on the **subchapters**:
 - Definition of Motivation;
 - Coaching.

- **In Chapter “Time Management”**, we will focus on the **subchapters**:
 - How Important is Time Management?;
 - Tips to Improve your Skills.

By the end of this module, you will be able to:

- ◆ Learn the concept of Emotional Intelligence
- ◆ Recognise the five elements of Emotional Intelligence
- ◆ Learn the difference between Verbal and Nonverbal Communication
- ◆ Define the concept of Conflict
- ◆ Learn Conflict Management
- ◆ Enable change after the Conflict
- ◆ Learn the concept of Motivation
- ◆ Comprehend what Coaching is
- ◆ Learn how important it is Time Management
- ◆ Comprehend tips on focusing energy

Chapter 1 - Emotional Intelligence

Sub-chapter 1.1 - Five Elements of Emotional Intelligence

Emotional Intelligence, the ability to recognise, manage/regulate, and express one's own and others' emotions,¹ is a critical competency for a **leader**, as it capacitates people to better conduct interpersonal relationships wisely and empathetically. Thus, Emotional Intelligence is crucial for effective leadership since it is nearly an “all-in-one” skill.

You should always be looking for ways to **improve your Emotional Intelligence**, even if you already have a lot of it. As a result, your leadership potential will rise, as will the quality of your interpersonal interactions. You can develop stronger connections and deal with challenging situations more successfully if you have a greater level of Emotional Intelligence.

There are **five elements that Emotional Intelligence** comprises, which help define desirable Leadership competencies. They are:¹

Figure 1. Five Elements of Emotional Intelligence

1. Self-Awareness^{1,2}

The first step in improving Emotional Intelligence and boosting your chances of being a great leader is to become **aware of our own and other people's emotions**. Emotional knowledge is the process of understanding moods and emotions and developing and changing through time. When faced with a significant choice, you may have been told to “keep your mind calm”, which is a common request from others, but why? We must be aware that emotions may obscure or distort our judgments, and those objective facts may be distorted. When trying to get a group of individuals to work together towards a similar objective, it is vital to understand how emotions drive people and their behaviours.

For example, as a leader, do you help your colleagues to make connections between the way they feel and the quality of the service they provide? When you are angered, you may express your frustrations towards your colleagues and inmates. Being aware of these emotions is crucial to better deal with different situations.

2. Self-Regulation^{1,2}

Emotional intelligence needs self-awareness and the ability to **manage and use one's emotions effectively**. For example, emotions may be beneficial in directing attention to urgent problems and communicating what should be the focus of attention. Emotions, on the other hand, may be utilised to make choices and make decisions. Positive emotions can help with creative thinking, integrative thinking, and inductive reasoning, while negative emotions can help pay attention to the finer points, detect errors, and carefully digest information.

Prison leaders need to develop above-average interpersonal skills. How do you deal with your emotions daily can impact the relationships with your colleagues and inmates? If you are not well emotionally, you cannot support a staff member emotionally in need,

which will potentially increase the difficulties of dealing with the emotional burnout (both from you and your team member).

There is a significant number of inmates with mental health issues. Likewise, correctional staff considers it crucial to understand mental health issues to deal better with the inmates and respond more effectively to their needs. As a leader, you should enhance your knowledge of alert signs to respond more effectively. Emotional management skills are essential for a successful leader.

3. Motivation^{1,2}

Emotions have a significant influence on **self-motivation**. When you are distracted by your emotions, you may find it difficult to complete activities. As a leader, you must be willing to work hard and set an example for your employees to follow. These jobs require a high level of self-motivation and determination.

It is tough to be a leader when your team is not driven. It might be not easy to keep staff motivated. Prison leaders (for example, prison governors and officers) are responsible individually and collectively for what happens in their institutions. You need to acknowledge, communicate, and celebrate successful changes, even when partial.

As a leader, you should be able to manage your team members' expectations, and for that, you will need to promote your active listening skills.

4. Empathy^{1,2}

Leaders aspire to be good “people folks” because being a successful leader includes managing one’s sentiments and managing the moods and emotions of others. The ability to excite, inspire, or make them feel cautious is an essential interpersonal skill and a social influence tool. **In order to demonstrate to their employees that they care about their needs and goals, leaders need to have empathy.** To be empathetic, one must recognise other people’s feelings and comprehend them. To be aware of people, their needs, and what they have gone through, authentic leaders must also possess empathy.

But it may be challenging to demonstrate empathy in the prison context. The deprivation of liberty makes inmates dependent on the detaining authorities to respect their fundamental human rights. Prison authorities, therefore, have a responsibility to ensure that treatment and care while in detention are fair and respect inmates' rights.

Clear communication with staff and inmates on all aspects of prison rules is essential. When people are well aware of their roles and what is expected from them, it tends to be less confusion and greater effectiveness in performing duties. Despite following the rules and procedures, you will understand the importance of empathy as you talk and act considering the other person's thinking, feelings and emotions.

5. Interpersonal Skills^{1,2}

When we speak and engage with other individuals, individually or in groups, we use interpersonal skills. **Interpersonal skills include communication and listening abilities, attitude and behaviour, among many other talents.** Leading others requires exposure and good communication with them. Knowledge of social expectations and norms is a prerequisite for interpersonal skills since they consider how other people react to change their approach or communications accordingly.

As a sort of social intelligence, interpersonal skills rely on paying attention to the actions and words of others and accurately understanding it to formulate a response. A person's personality and intuition¹ play a role in developing these talents, but they also come through life experience and education.

Good leaders are guided by their values and base their decisions on facts. They can be decisive without being authoritarian. Even within your task, sometimes it is better to explain and communicate your decisions.

Various issues are associated with the prison layout and conditions for vulnerable inmates. For example, some of the physical features of the prison may hinder physically disabled offenders from satisfying their basic needs, and clear interpersonal skills can be of added value to surpass difficulties.

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes and check your progress in the next page...

What did I learn?

- ◆ The Five Elements of Emotional Intelligence

Chapter 2 - What is Communication?

Sub-chapter 2.1 - Verbal and Nonverbal Communication

Communication is a word deriving from Latin *communicare* – sharing and making known, so other people may know what you know. There are different types of communication; for example, in **written communication**, we use written symbols, such as e-mail or letters, or in publications such as newspapers, magazines, or books. When you **communicate verbally**, you utilise vocal signals (what we say verbally). Our body language, tone of voice and intonation are some of the nonverbal indicators we communicate **nonverbally**.^{1,3} Communication can be **intrapersonal** or **interpersonal**, depending on the participants.^{1,2}

Figure 2. Types of Communication

Intrapersonal communication refers to **communication between and inside individuals** and hence only defines communication in a limited sense.^{1,2} **Interpersonal communication** is a form of **direct, one-on-one communication between couples or small groups**. There are a variety of interpersonal communication skills that can help you communicate effectively with others.^{1,2}

Much communication takes place **verbally**. We use words and symbols to convey our message. Some words and symbols have meaning for those who speak the same

language³ However, it may not be so obvious in **non-verbal** communication. Individuals may not be giving enough attention to non-verbal cues, for example. As such, nonverbal communication may not seem significant to us.³

Across nations and ethnicities, facial expressions tend to be similar and interpreted the same way. **Facial expressions** are the fastest method to receive signals and the easiest way to convey our degree of knowledge or engagement in the conversation.³

Body Movements and Posture – when you stand or move in a certain way or even hold your head in a certain way, you send a message that cannot be heard. Our **body language** and **posture** convey our thoughts, feelings, and relationships between the persons participating in the discussion.^{1, 2} An anxious leader usually generates anxious feelings in others (and the opposite also happens: employees can be emotionally contagious/influenced if the leader is happy and confident). That is the extent to which leaders can influence others!

✔ **Openness/Confidence**

- ◆ Maintain Eye Contact
- ◆ Legs apart while Standing
- ◆ Leaning Forward
- ◆ Smile/Relaxed
- ◆ Nod when listening

✘ **Closed Gestures/Insecurity**

- ◆ Looking down or away
- ◆ Standing Leg Cross
- ◆ Arm Crossed
- ◆ Leaning Back
- ◆ Patting/Fondling Hair
- ◆ Biting Nails, Putting objects in the mouth

Figure 3. Little Dictionary of Body Language

Gestures are the most expressive nonverbal communication, second only to facial emotions. It may be used alone, without a verbal message accompanying it. Alternatively, it may be utilised to make a spoken message more powerful by expressing movements or emphasising it. When we are disputing or speaking animatedly, for example, we wave, point, call, and use our hands. Gestures are a common way we communicate ourselves without even realising it. It is crucial to remember that gestures might have quite varied meanings between cultures and locations.^{1,2}

In nonverbal communication, **eye contact** is essential. You may express curiosity, affection, hatred or desire via the way you look at someone. **Maintaining eye contact is essential** to sustain the flow of a discussion and gauge the other person's response.^{1,2}

Other nonverbal communication techniques include **touch**. If you think about it, a strong handshake, an innocuous touch on the shoulder, or a loving bear embrace may all send different messages. In addition, touch may inspire others to take action or reduce the gap between individuals and improve the contact by expressing our feelings such as belonging, anger, caring, love, fear, etc.^{1,2,4}

Even though we all want **physical space**, that requirement changes based on culture, situation and degree of intimacy in a given relationship. Many nonverbal cues may be sent through physical space, such as closeness, aggressiveness, dominance or affection.^{1,2,4}

Important communication aspects include **voice**: paralinguistic signals such as pitch, loudness, inflexion, rhythm and pace. In addition to hearing our words, other individuals

can “read” our voices. Through this tiny but strong nonverbal speech, we may gain insight into our genuine sentiments and what we truly mean. The tone of your voice may convey many different emotions such as aroused wrath, love or self-assurance.^{1,3}

Since every person is unique, they communicate in different ways as well (verbally and nonverbally). The general rules mentioned above may be valid for certain cultures and individuals, but they may not be for others. Nonetheless, it is also vital to remember that nonverbal cues may not necessarily indicate the same thing in every scenario.

Be on the lookout for nonverbal cues from the other person about what is acceptable and not. For example, if a person is continuously taking a step back while talking to you, it might imply that he/she is uncomfortable with the amount of personal space and would want more. It is vital to be mindful of the other person’s requests and to double-check your assumptions.

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

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Sub-chapter 2.2 - Clearly Communication

Communication occurs only when someone hears, listens to, and comprehends the message and when nonverbal cues accompany the message. Listening is an essential ability in our interactions with others. According to an adage, “we have two ears but only one mouth; therefore, we can listen twice as much as we talk.” **The capacity to correctly hear and comprehend signals throughout the communication process is referred to as listening.**

As the name implies, **active listening** involves paying close attention to verbal and nonverbally messages. In order to ensure that the identical message is received on the other side, it is necessary to comprehend the message, confirm this comprehension, and provide feedback on what has been heard.¹ As a leader, you have to listen and communicate clearly to people (for example, what is the task, the situation, and what you expect your team to do). You need to recognise people’s work by providing feedback on the work done, and you can even prevent or solve conflicts that arise from different situations.

In prison, when you communicate clearly, everyone should understand what you mean, allowing you to discuss the problem (if it exists) and solve them together. By listening to your team members, you can also involve other people in the decision-making, even if the final decision making is up to you. In these cases, an adequate leader presents the idea to be discussed with those accountable for the final decision. If clear and frontal, this communication channel can be a way to promote a good and healthy workplace.

Giving and Receiving Feedback^{1,2}

A leader’s ability to provide and receive feedback is a crucial communication skill. The requirement for appropriate feedback is unavoidable as a member of an organisation and as a leader of your team. Whether we want someone’s opinion on our work or we need to analyse the behaviour of others, understanding how to offer positive and useful feedback and how to take constructive criticism from others is a valuable ability.

When delivering feedback, the most effective is the one that is clearly heard, understood, and accepted - these are the areas in which you, as the feedback giver, have control. You have no influence over whether the receiver acts on your input. It is their job to take care of such aspects.

The following criteria characterise effective feedback:

1. Feedback is about behaviour, not personality - The first and most essential rule of feedback is to remember that you are not commenting on who they are, what they think, or what they value. You are simply remarking on how they acted. Do not be tempted to talk about your personality, intelligence, or anything else. It's only behaviour.

2. Feedback should illustrate the effect of the individual's behaviour on you - It is not as if you are privy to anyone's or anything else's reaction to it. Just how you felt or thought about it, that is all you have to go on! Feedback is simpler to hear and accept when presented as your viewpoint. After all, neither they nor you have any influence over how you feel. This is a no-fault zone for everyone involved.

3. Feedback should be as precise as possible - We all know it is tempting to start from the perspective that "everything you do is garbage", especially when things are not going well but do not. For starters, that is not true. You will find excellent and even amazing things this person accomplishes if you are honest with yourself and honestly judge other

people’s behaviour or contributions. Consider particular events and behaviours and write down exactly what the individual did and how you felt as a result. The more specific you can be, the better.

4. Feedback should be timely - It is pointless telling someone about something that irritated or delighted you six months ago. Feedback must be given as soon as possible, while everyone is still aware of what occurred. It is also a great idea to think of a good time to express anything you want to say. An angry individual, for example, will refuse to receive feedback, no matter how skillfully delivered. Wait until they have settled down a little. **When offering feedback, we must keep three forms of communication in mind.**

They are as follows:^{1, 2}

Figure 4. Three Forms of Communication when Providing Feedback

- **Passive Communication**

Compliance with the wishes of others can undermine individual rights and self-confidence. Those who are passive fail to convey their views and feelings, which leads them to do things they do not want to do in the hopes of pleasing others. Due to their preference for others’ rights, wants, and feelings over their own, such individuals do not see themselves as equals. They let others take responsibility, lead and make choices for them.

- **Aggressive Communication**

The rights and self-esteem of others are undermined. Aggressive behaviour seldom shows respect or appreciation for others, and aggressive responses tend to put others down. Aggressive behaviours include rushing someone excessively, telling rather than asking, disregarding someone, and failing to consider another's feelings.

- **Assertive Communication**

Being assertive implies being able to speak up for your own or other people's rights pleasantly and peacefully, without being confrontational or passively accepting "wrong". It entails considering your own and other people's rights, aspirations, desires, requirements, and wishes. It also entails encouraging people to be open and honest about their thoughts, needs, and feelings for both parties to behave correctly. Among the assertive behaviours, there are:

- ◆ Being open in communicating desires, thoughts and emotions and encouraging other people to do similarly
- ◆ Pay attention to the opinions of other people and responding properly, whether in agreement with those views or not
- ◆ Taking responsibilities and being capable to assign to others
- ◆ Frequently expressing admiration of other people for what they have accomplished
- ◆ Being able to acknowledge mistakes and apologise
- ◆ Maintaining self-control
- ◆ Behaving as an equal to others

For example, part of your job as a leader is to manage shifts and tasks. You are required to escort an inmate to court. Therefore, you need to select a person to do the job. If the person has doubts, you should be clear in the clarification, and be available anytime to provide feedback on what went wrong, if necessary, without being overpowering.

- **I-Messages: Shifting the Focus**

We frequently accuse, criticise, and point fingers in direct conversation with others. To be effective leaders, we must learn to be open and accepting of other people's points of view while remaining strong in expressing our own. I-messages communicate by diverting the emphasis

away from the other person and toward us. Instead of criticising and seeking for what the other person did wrong, we may successfully demonstrate how a certain event has affected us and how we hope it will be handled in the future.

Examples of shifting the focus:^{1,2}

- ◆ Behaviour that affected you (*When you...*)
- ◆ Feelings it provoked (*I feel...*)
- ◆ Consequence/effect (*Because...*)
- ◆ Future desired behaviour (*I need/I wish/ I would prefer...*)

Remember: I-messages are utilised to improve the situation, communication, and relationships. Take cautious not to use them as a kind of emotional blackmail. “Being taken advantage of” is you-message disguised as a feeling: “You are taking advantage of me!” Joy, sorrow, anger, contempt, love, humiliation, surprise, fear, and other emotions are examples of feelings, so be cautious when using them.

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes and check your progress in the next page...

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What did I learn?

- ◆ Definition and characteristics of Communication
- ◆ Definition and characteristics of Verbal Communication
- ◆ Definition and characteristics of Nonverbal Communication
- ◆ Definition and characteristics of Clear Communication

Chapter 3 - How to Solve Conflicts?

Sub-chapter 3.1 - Defining Conflict

When we hear the term **conflict**, we immediately think of negative connotations such as violence, devastation, and irreconcilable disagreements. Conflict may be harmful, causing individuals to acquire unfavourable sentiments for one another. It can also exacerbate divisions and cause groups to polarise into either/or stances. On the other hand, a **disagreement** may be beneficial, assisting in "clearing the air", releasing emotion and stress, and relieving tension, especially if those involved utilise it as a chance to enhance understanding and find a path ahead together. Conflicts have the potential to be beneficial and are an essential component of healthy interpersonal relationships, creative problem resolution, and group cohesion.^{1,2}

Conflict is caused by people's wants and desires, which are frequently contradictory and therefore in conflict. People's values, the rules by which they live their lives and engage socially with others, are closely connected to needs. Needs and values are not always obvious and explicit. People like to communicate by adopting particular stances, which are only evident in their behaviour, appearance, and communication style. However, there is much more of what stays buried beneath the surface. People hold their positions far more tenaciously in a conflict environment since they can be defended. Needs (especially emotional or personal ones) may appear to be a sign of weakness, or they may be more strategically disguised. People may also lose sight of their needs when they grow so focused on bolstering their status that their needs get hidden.

Figure 5. Tip of the Iceberg Example to Explain Conflict

Figure 6. Tip of the Iceberg Example to Explain Conflict

Check Your Assumptions and Connect at the Aspirations^{1, 2}

- **Positions** - The difficulty with positions is that they nearly always generate automatic antagonism; for every stance, there is an opposite one. Conflict exists at the position level and is rarely addressed at that level. At this stage, one half must completely abandon its own stance, or the two must meet somewhere in the middle, with each believing they have compromised.
- **Assumptions** - Underlying beliefs frequently influence people's positions. These frequently involve several assumptions regarding the other party's intentions. Examine your preconceptions. If you start questioning your assumptions, you could discover that you were completely incorrect. It is difficult to predict another person's wants and intentions. Rather than assuming, it is important to check with them.
- **Aspirations** - The underlying desires that fuel our viewpoints hold the secret to reaping the benefits of conflict. While it is a natural human response to oppose another person's strict viewpoint, we react somewhat differently to ambitions, which

are tough to disagree with. Each of us is hardwired to support the genuinely felt goals of others. Consider how often you have instantly rooted for complete strangers you have read about or seen in a movie that is passionately pursuing a dream. At the level of aspiration, humans have a great deal of common ground.

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

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Sub-chapter 3.2 - Conflict Management

Conflict Management

Most people often avoid conflict and possibly unpleasant circumstances - it is human nature. In contrast, putting off conflict resolution and challenging communication circumstances can lead to emotions of frustration, guilt, irritation with oneself, rage and a loss of self-confidence, as well as an increase in tension or worry and the possibility of a larger dispute in the future. In a prison, fairness and transparency are required to deal with staff and inmates' grievances.

Early dispute resolution is typically easier since the viewpoints are less entrenched, and the negative emotions are not as severe as later on. **Negotiation** between the parties is the most effective approach to resolve a problem in its early phases.¹

Strategies in Dealing with Conflict:¹

- **Competing** - It is a zero-sum game where one side wins and the other loses when it comes to competition. As a conflict management approach, very aggressive people typically resort to competition. Everybody in this scenario is determined to win the debate and obtain what they want, without or with little regard for the opposing side. The discipline required within a prison must be balanced with a strong sense of mutual respect and safety. Therefore, the competing type of strategy may not be appropriate to deal with conflicts and need to be used very carefully.

Concern for self: HIGH	Competing	Collaborating
	Compromising	
Concern for self: LOW	Avoiding	Accommodating
	Concern for others: LOW	Concern for other: HIGH

Figure 7. Competing Characteristics

- **Accommodating** - Also a win-lose situation, accommodating approach is the reverse of competing. In other words, you have to give the other side what it wants. While being accommodating, we put the needs of others above our own. Our desire to maintain calm or our perception of a minor problem might lead us to accommodate. This technique works well when the other person is an expert or has a better answer.

It is possible that people who utilise accommodation as their major conflict management approach would get resentful because they believe their demands were not satisfied and their opinions were not taken into account. considered. Therefore, all those involved (down to the front-line level) must receive clear directions and develop an understanding of how they themselves can contribute to the overall goal/conflict resolution. Without a shared sense of direction, the support for the proposed change will vanish quickly. Conflicting priorities cannot be tolerated.

- **Avoiding** - Confrontation avoidance is a technique that aims to put off conflict for as long as possible. The avoider thinks that by postponing or avoiding the dispute, it will resolve itself without a confrontation. Instead of assisting the other person to achieve their goals, we are pursuing our own without any assertiveness. When the problem is minor, or you have no chance of winning, this strategy works. Also, it can be effective when the problem is exceedingly expensive to fix. If the atmosphere is emotionally charged, and you need to create some space, it is a great way! In certain cases, difficulties will resolve themselves, but ignoring them, in general, is not a wise long-term approach for solving conflict.

- **Collaborating** - Ideas from different individuals are combined to create a cohesive whole. A win-win approach is to come up with a creative solution that is acceptable to everyone. Collaboration, while beneficial, requires a considerable time investment that is not suited for all disputes, and in particular sorts of conflicts, a win-win scenario cannot be reached in the conventional sense.

- **Compromising** - According to this approach, both parties of a disagreement must compromise in order to reach an acceptable, if not unanimous, settlement. If both sides get at least some of their demands satisfied, then compromising is the “second” best choice.

Any conflict that arises should be dealt with in a timely and fair manner and in a way that protects personal privacy and support whenever possible and appropriates some informal resolution of the conflict in a mutually satisfactory way for all parties involved. Each conflict resolution strategy has its merits and downsides, however we should consider each for the sake of conflict resolution.

Negotiation or Mediation:¹

- **Negotiation** is the process of finding a solution that is acceptable to all parties concerned. Negotiation’s goal is to get to an agreement without creating future communication hurdles. When it gets to negotiations, there is a big difference between them and mediation.
- **Mediation** is the engagement of a neutral third party to support and assist individuals engaged in a disagreement in finding a settlement. Third-party mediators assist them in coming to an agreement in mediation. The ability to mediate conflicts is a must-have for justice system leaders. For the benefit of the group as a whole, justice system leaders need to be prepared to intervene in a conflict situation.

Negotiation and mediation are alternatives to the use of force, including the peaceful settlement of conflicts, the understanding of crowd behaviour. So, they are of great value to prison staff and a prison leader.

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

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Sub-chapter 3.3 - Enabling Change after the Conflict

Leaders who can bring about change are required in every prison system. Effective change within organisations can only take place if relationships among people are based on mutual respect and trust.

Leaders must think strategically, take the time to properly plan and learn to anticipate obstacles and difficulties as well as the inertia and the resistance that they will necessarily encounter in bringing about change in an essentially conservative environment.¹

- **Balancing Priorities**^{1, 2}

Keeping a solid balance between short-term and long-term improvement and is critical leadership ability. Weakness in strategic thinking leads to organisational myopia and the danger of missing out on the next great thing.

- **Maintaining Stability**^{1, 2}

When it comes to short- and long-term change, the leader strives to preserve equilibrium. Even while most people are willing to accept minor changes that enhance the way things are done, major changes need the leader to motivate people for many years before they see a return. Discussions with those involved in the potential change should be conducted

prior to adopting a change to determine its consequences. Individuals should be able to ask questions and voice their concerns without fear of repercussions. It is important to show them what will remain the same so that they may feel more secure.

Being able to draw from the best abilities and characteristics of team members and staff to establish a team spirit among them so that they work well together in cooperation as opposed to competing with each other is not an easy task for a leader. Empowering others and building the capacity of various teams to accomplish complex tasks means maintaining the stability of the change for her to remain on time and be sustainable.

- **Reacting to Change**^{1,2}

To change, everyone has a distinct reaction. Innovative people sometimes go to extremes and do not realise that no one has followed them. Only when everyone else has left, do the stragglers show up.

Traditionalists view change as a danger and want to hold on to the past for as long as possible. Their emotional response to the approaching shift is surprising, like that of the inventors. Other people—the more cautious majority—are prone to evaluate arguments using logic.

- **Adjusting Plans**^{1,2}

When expressing your ideas as a leader, you need to employ both reasoning and passion. Maintain a positive attitude and remind everyone of the benefits after the changes are implemented. Individuals adjust to change at varying rates, so you should be prepared for the long haul. The adjustment process is generally divided into phases,

each of which is characterised by a particular set of behaviours. Others who embrace change quickly may get impatient with those who do not, which can lead to conflict within the team, which you may be called upon to help mediate if the situation arises.

In sum, prison leaders can provide direction and effect important change by leading the development of prison policies, reviewing and amending operation policies, directives, and standing orders and setting mechanisms to communicate these policies and ensure their effective implementation.

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes and check your progress in the next page...

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What did I learn?

- ◆ Definition and characteristics of Conflict
- ◆ How to manage a Conflict (Strategies in Dealing with Conflict Competing)
- ◆ The difference between Negotiation and Mediation
- ◆ How to enable change after the Conflict

Chapter 4 - How important is Motivation?

Sub-chapter 4.1 - Definition of Motivation

Motivation refers to the desires or requirements that drive behaviour toward a particular objective. It is a strong want to behave or act in a way that would fulfil specific circumstances, such as wishes, objectives, or goals. Older motivation theories held that logical intellect and reason were the leading elements in human motivation. However, psychologists today believe that motivation is founded on basic urges to maximise well-being, minimise physical discomfort, and maximise pleasure.²

The **Hierarchy of Needs**¹ is one paradigm used to analyse motivation. Humans are inherently motivated to better themselves and move toward expressing their full potential — self-actualisation — by encountering and satisfying various levels of needs, ranging from the most basic, such as food and safety, to higher-order needs such as love, belonging, and self-esteem.

Figure 8. Hierarchy of Needs

This idea was expanded to include a desire for self-transcendence: people achieve the pinnacle of growth and find the most significance in life by paying attention to things other than themselves. Although the theory's universality has been questioned, many people feel it reflects essential facts about the human drive.

Typically, motivation is broken down into two categories: drives and motivations. The **drive** results from physiological factors such as hunger and drowsiness, as well as the urge to reproduce. All of these factors influence our decision to engage in particular activities. Individual drives may be **self-motivated** and not dependent on external stimuli.

Social and psychological factors such as job, family life, and relationships have a major role in motives. Praise and approbation are two of them.¹

Stimulation and deprivation can be used to influence both drives and motivations. Shock, loud noise, and extreme heat or cold might encourage us to seek out better situations. Positive or enjoyable environments can also boost motivation (such as food). In addition, we get driven when something we desire or need is taken away from us, such as appropriate nourishment or social interaction.

- **Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation**

Motivation can be **intrinsic** (internal factors) or **extrinsic** (external factors).¹ Self-satisfaction generates intrinsically motivated activities driven by the enjoyment they provide. A person's interest or delight in the work itself is what drives them. A prison guard that likes its job and functions, for example, enjoys studying and wants to develop the skills to improve and go further in the correctional career path. **Intrinsic motivation** is an essential factor in cognitive, social, and physical growth; intrinsically driven persons are more likely to perform well and increase their abilities at a particular activity.

Contrarily, activities with an **extrinsic motivation** aim to get something from others. Instead of coming from the person, they originate from the outside world – from other humans. You may work because you want to be paid, rather than because you like it.

You may be good at your job because you want to achieve the job promotion that is open. You are not motivated by the intrinsic joy you obtain from doing your tasks and job. For example, if you are participating in this training to improve your leadership skills, you will probably want an increase in your pay, or you wish to apply these new skills you acquired in your job, your motive is more external.

Figure 9. Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation

A mix of internal and extrinsic variables are typically at work when it comes to motivating us, and this balance can alter over time. You may love your job as a prison guard or director, and you may spend extra hours working. You love what you do, but a new position opens, and you decide to apply to that position. For your job, you are now receiving an extrinsic reward (such as payment), and you may find yourself becoming more extrinsically driven over time. This phenomenon is recognised as the over justification effect. Ultimately, this can lead to the loss of intrinsic motivation and dependence on extrinsic rewards for continued performance – like money or others recognition. Good leaders are people who can inspire their staff and who are able to offer their staff a sense of self-worth and personal value. They know how to build strong teams of committed professionals who are dedicated to the objectives and are not afraid of change.

Figure 10. Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation

- **Motivation VS Emotion¹**

While motivation and emotion might be closely intertwined, they are essentially separate entities that must be understood. An **emotion** corresponds to a subjective state of being that we frequently refer to as a feeling, whereas **motivation** defines the wants or needs that guide action toward an end objective. The relationship between emotion and motivation is complex: both impact behaviour and can lead to action, and emotion can function as a motivator in and of itself. People might be motivated to get out of a difficult situation by fear or by the emotion of enjoyment.

The fact is that many leaders do not want to share responsibility because they do not want to lose any of their authority. One of the most challenging tasks for new supervisors is “giving up” control when faced with a vital assignment. Leaders who are competent facilitators learn to think beyond their interests for the benefit of the group they manage. Unfortunately, many leaders continue to fail to recognise the immediate benefits of such action.

It is also evident that organisations cannot simply declare individuals to be empowered. Leaders cannot encourage people to be inventive, willing to take risks or adopt courses of action that are unpleasant for them. Individuals must empower themselves in this regard because organisational change begins with self-transformation. The work of the organisation is a priority for an empowered workforce. Personnel is motivated by a sense

of competence and a belief that they are learning and developing their skills. They are making decisions that directly impact them. There is a sense of belonging and personal significance, and they find purpose in what they do and who they are as people. Organisational leaders who inspire their employees to achieve their best are bringing out the best in the organisation.

Enabler Leaders recognise that they cannot accomplish organisational greatness by themselves. Their leadership skills grow because of sharing leadership in the organisation. More essential tasks, such as strategic thinking and problem-solving, may be accomplished with the freed-up time. By fostering cooperation, supporting cooperative aims, and developing trust in their connections, sharing leadership empowers others. “We” rather than “I” is encouraged by leaders.^{3, 4}

In reality, the most significant accomplishments of efficient and productive leaders are derived from the successes of their workers. To **empower individuals**, you must allow them to bring their expertise and experience to work and encourage them to apply it for organisational responsibilities.

Encouragement and empowerment are also part of the equation. It is only when individuals are empowered that they can realise their full potential. Having a strong belief in others is the most important component for leaders who want to empower others. This increases their self-confidence.^{3, 4}

Unselfish leadership at the top and a high degree of competence are required to be willing to dedicate time, resources and energy and to the growth of staff leadership. Individuals who are empowered are more likely to progress in their careers, leading to creativity and change. People are uneasy with change since it is the price of development. For some leaders, this uneasy feeling prevents them from completing their leadership development inside the organisation as a result of it.

There is little doubt that an empowered leader cannot simply assign responsibilities without guiding them. A constant effort is made to reconcile employee autonomy with appropriate levels of responsibility in employee empowerment and leadership development initiatives. Achieving this balance is not easy. For people to be successful,

they must be given the appropriate training and resources. Ongoing learning is a key element of a well-functioning, empowered prison. With the right tools, chiefs may develop into leaders, and guards can begin to accomplish achievements formerly seen as impossible. ^{3, 4}

Figure 11. Leadership Requires Time, Resources and Energy and to the Growth of Staff Leadership

In a culture of empowerment, strategic choices are still made by the top leadership. But as they get more comfortable taking on the accompanying risks, guards should become more involved in making operational choices. More and more critical choices are being made by persons at lower and lower staff levels. Technological advancements are facilitating this decision-making reality. To reduce their engagement in decision-making when staff begin to take on more responsibility for decisions and their repercussions, leaders must progressively reduce their involvement. Essentially, this is a process of role transformation.

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes/observations.

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Sub-chapter 4.2 - Coaching

Increasing prison staff empowerment and greater performance have made it obvious that **leadership plays a crucial role**. This condition may be encouraged and supported when organisational leaders serve as “coaches.” Someone can be coached in order to attain a goal, enhance their performance, learn new skills, or take on new responsibilities.¹

As a prison strives to enhance internal engagement, the lead coach is typically more effective in his/her leadership role. In other words, it is the antithesis of “command and control.” A coach’s role is to assist each person in developing their talents, ownership of tasks, responsibility, authority, and purpose to increase the quality of work. The objective of successful coaching is to empower the staff as part of a well-functioning “team”.²

Some people are fortunate enough to get a formal education in coaching. Although many leaders must learn this crucial competence on their own, there are a few exceptions. As a leader, this starts with self-awareness. Prior to being able to help others, you must first understand yourself, how people see you, and your own strengths and limitations. If you want others to emulate you, you must be a role model for them.

The second level of becoming a leader coach entails building your personal growth plan to capitalise on your strengths and address any deficiencies. Once you have a personal development plan in place, you can begin working with your team members to create similar goals for them.³

While a strategic plan is being formulated, the coachee can prepare their own personal strategic plan, which sits inside the larger prison’s overall strategic plan. If you want to teach effectively, you need to know what your staff can do, understand what they are

capable of, and relate it to their personal or professional goals. Leader coaches assist their staff in setting long-term goals and devising a strategy for achieving them. When it comes to implementing development goals, they set expectations with their staff and provide the required training and feedback to ensure success. There is an art to following through, even if it may sound easy. The challenge is to do so despite the daily routine activity, which is common for most organisational leaders to encounter.³

Coaching people are more aware of their role in the correctional setting's vision, purpose, and strategy. As guards and other staff become more aware of and devoted to their specific areas of responsibility, the organisation's success will continue to grow. Coaches' implicit message, "I trust in you, and I demand your best efforts", has led to this dedication. Employees are usually up to the task.

Coaching leaders are, by definition, skilled at delegating; they offer workers difficult tasks, even if it means the tasks will take longer to complete. In other words, these leaders are ready to accept short-term failure in order to advance long-term learning. Effective management of the prison necessarily involves organising staff, what their jobs are to be and how best to manage them. Distinguishing between various functions is a way to delegate authority which can help in the efficient allocation of resources and make staff more accountable for their actions. They are less likely to blame someone else for not doing a task if that task is theirs in the first place.²

Within an organisation, there are five main forms of coaching:⁴

Figure 12. Five Main Forms of Coaching

- **Performance coaching** – is utilised when a person needs help getting back on track. An attitude problem is generally the culprit here, rather than a problem with their talents.
- **Development coaching** – high-performing individuals that want to enhance their talents in their present position. This is crucial for the development of future leaders in the company. Therefore, it is important for leaders to establish a process for the effective delegation of authority to trusted and capable individuals, and for supporting these individuals in carrying out their delegated duties.
- **Career coaching** – when people are ready to plan their future professional steps. This is a key approach for keeping organisational talent; when individuals think and discuss their future, they become more motivated to continue improving. Being able to draw from the best abilities and characteristics of team members and staff, to establish a team spirit among them so that they work well together in cooperation as opposed to competing with each other, is somehow crucial to prevent people from leaving. One of the major reasons that great performers quit an organisation is that they were not asked to stay, or they feel that they do not belong.
- **Coaching to support learning** – management promotes and supports recent training by encouraging staff to practice what they have learned. Personnel development is aided through education, which is one of the most effective strategies to develop prison staff. The increased responsibility and personal accomplishment in turn can also have a positive effect on staff morale and job satisfaction. In some cases, specialisation should be supported through knowledge and skills training as part of the personnel development program for facilitating a career in the service. At the same time, prison leaders should ensure that staff have experience in a number of different areas and not be stuck in one job just because they are experts in it.
- **Creating an internal coaching culture** - occurs when leaders see the benefits of coaching and use it to improve others. Coaching emphasises leadership development and promotes a mentality of accepting ownership and responsibility for one's job. When difficulties emerge, a coaching culture emphasises self-responsibility rather

than criticising or pointing the finger at others. Taking up self-responsibility typically results in a more productive and happy work atmosphere.

However, the leader as a coach must also be mindful of when to enable and when to “back off” and allow someone to sort something out independently. When individuals are “up for it,” the coaching approach works effectively in various organisational settings. Guards who know their limitations and want to enhance their performance, for example, benefit from the coaching approach. When prison staff realise that developing new skills would help them advance, the method works effectively.

When employees, for whatever reason, are unwilling to learn or change their habits, the coaching approach makes little sense. For example, some prison officials sometimes see their obligation to provide information to inmates as a hindrance to their efforts to keep inmates under control. However, maintaining control over the inmates needs not to be opposed to upholding their rights. Maintaining a balance between ensuring control and upholding the rights of inmates is what distinguishes a progressive and confident leadership from one that is weak and fearful. If the leader lacks the competence to guide a team member, it won't function. Coaching is a skill that many managers lack, especially when it comes to providing continual performance criticism that inspires rather than creates dread or indifference.

Only a small number of people have been trained on being successful coaches despite the importance of coaching to the organisation and its workers. Due to its time and talent requirements, the coaching style of leadership is often ignored. Most people discover that they do not need to spend any more time after the first session. Leaders who disregard this approach are missing out on a great tool to motivate their team members.

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes and check your progress in the next page...

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What did I learn?

- ◆ Definition and characteristics of Motivation
- ◆ The difference between Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation
- ◆ The difference between Motivation and Emotion
- ◆ Definition and characteristics of Coaching
- ◆ Definition and characteristics of Coaching leaders

Chapter 5 - Time Management

Sub-chapter 5.1 - How Important is Time Management?

Every decision concerning human and financial resources made by prison leaders ultimately has an impact on the inmates as well as staff. All decisions with financial or human resources implications ought to be aligned with the priorities dictated by the responsibility of prison leaders for the welfare and safety of inmates and staff, the security of the institution and public safety objectives.

In making decisions about how to use limited funds available, prison leaders must often make difficult decisions. In all instances, people's basic needs and safety should take priority. Of course, at times, everything will be equally urgent and important, and in these conditions, a clear plan of what needs to be done and in what order is still needed.

Managing time is similar to managing life: we strike the best balance between what needs to be done and what we like doing. Allocating time operates similarly; it must be effective and well balanced in accordance with the objective demands of the tasks at hand.^{1,2}

When it comes to time management, there are a few things to keep in mind:^{1,2}

Figure 13. Few Things to Keep in Mind About Time Management

You should also be aware that your coworkers and volunteers may not feel the same way about your tasks and function, even if you have a lot of free time. You should not anticipate or demand that they commit more time than they are willing to devote themselves to.

As for your **personal time**, take care not to overextend yourself. There will be moments when your tasks and function will require a lot of effort, so you may need to allocate additional time to them before and during those times. To counteract this, try to alternate times of intense work with moments of relaxation and time-out. Not only will you prevent burnout and job overload, but it will also help you maintain the efficacy of your task and function and the connections you have built with other people.

Take notes/observations of this sub-chapter:

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Sub-chapter 5.2 - Tips to Improve Your Skills

You will almost certainly be bombarded with communications, requests, new responsibilities, and tasks as a leader. Recognising — and focusing on — what is truly essential is key to your and your team’s success; it is critical that how you spend your time reflects your priorities.

Figure 14. How to Prioritize Tasks

Managing Your Time^{1, 2}

It is easy to become diverted from essential duties by less important but nevertheless urgent activities. Prioritising your actions is something you should do daily and with discipline. A straightforward approach is to make a “to-do” list at the end of each day. Examine this list, compare each item to your vision, values, and primary objectives, and rank each item in order of priority. Therefore, it is important for leaders to establish a time frame for an effective task assignment, and to support prison guards in carrying out their duties.

Working Smart^{1,2}

Figure 15. Do's and Dont's to Working Smart

Getting Back on Track^{1,2}

Recurring problems that you never seem to get around to resolving, are signs of poor time management. If the underlying reason is not addressed, your work life may quickly spiral out of control, draining your vitality and suffocating your creativity. Stop, take a breather, and redirect your thoughts. Make time to address strategic initiatives and consider what and how you might enhance delegating within your team.

Delegation is a crucial leadership skill that, when done correctly, offers significant advantages for both you and your team. It frees up your time, helps your team members feel appreciated, and builds talents in employees across the organisation. Delegating well involves more than simply passing overwork to a subordinate. Several aspects must be carefully considered before you act.

How to Delegate^{1,2}

- The person to whom you allocate a task should be appropriately selected. Assess the probability that things will not proceed as planned;
- Tasks should only be delegated if they are well stated. It is unrealistic to expect someone to succeed if you are unable to describe the intended goal and timeline;

- Rely on others to do time-consuming, repetitive activities;
- You should ensure that the individual to whom you are delegating understands what you are trying to accomplish;
- After you have delegated, you cannot abdicate responsibility;
- If you delegate, you are enabling others to discover their answers that may not be the same as yours;
- If things do not work out, do not blame anyone else;
- Assign and agree on goals, working methods, resources, and deadlines in advance.

Selecting Personnel^{1,2}

A “**Plan for Delegation**” can help you make an objective choice about which team member is most suited to take on a given work.

- Your team’s members should be listed;
- Choose someone based on a set of criteria - those included in the example table are a good place to start;
- Each member of your team should be granted a score from 1 to 10 for each of the criteria;
- Sum up the scores;
- Specify how much and what kind of training and development each individual needs. Sometimes the best candidate is not immediately apparent when you do this exercise. When it comes to finishing tasks, you may find yourself relying on just one experienced and talented team member. In contrast, others may have more time to spend on the work, gaining from the responsibility and experience.

Figure 16. Selecting Personnel

Verify if you learned everything required. Take notes and check your progress in the next page...

What did I learn?

- ◆ How important is Time Management
- ◆ Tips to improve your skills

References

Chapter 1 - Emotional Intelligence

Sub-chapter 1.1 - Five Elements of Emotional Intelligence

- ¹ Goleman, D. (2021). Leadership: The power of emotional intelligence. More Than Sound LLC.
- ² Kovač, H., Širol, M., & Šumanjski, M. (2017). Leadership Handbook. Sarajevo: South East European Youth Network. [Open Access] Retrieved from: https://www.salto-youth.net/downloads/toolbox_tool_download-file-1611/SEEYN%20LEADERSHIP%20HANDBOOK.pdf

Chapter 2 - What is Communication?

Sub-chapter 2.1 - Verbal and Nonverbal Communication

- ¹ Gilley, A., Gilley, J. W., & McMillan, H. S. (2009). Organisational change: Motivation, communication, and leadership effectiveness. *Performance Improvement Quarterly*, 21(4), 75–94. doi:10.1002/piq.20039
- ² Kovač, H., Širol, M., & Šumanjski, M. (2017). Leadership Handbook. Sarajevo: South East European Youth Network. [Open Access] Retrieved from: https://www.salto-youth.net/downloads/toolbox_tool_download-file-1611/SEEYN%20LEADERSHIP%20HANDBOOK.pdf
- ³ Lima, C. F., Arriaga, P., Anikin, A., Pires, A. R., Frade, S., Neves, L., & Scott, S. K. (2021). Authentic and Posed Emotional Vocalisations Trigger Distinct Facial Responses. *Cortex*, 141, 280-292. doi:10.1016/j.cortex.2021.04.015
- ⁴ Yaffe, P. (2011). The 7% rule: fact, fiction, or misunderstanding. *Ubiquity*. doi:10.1145/2043155.2043156

Sub-chapter 2.2 - Clearly Communication

- ¹ Gilley, A., Gilley, J. W., & McMillan, H. S. (2009). Organisational change: Motivation, communication, and leadership effectiveness. *Performance Improvement Quarterly*, 21(4), 75–94. doi:10.1002/piq.20039

² Kovač, H., Širol, M., & Šumanjski, M. (2017). Leadership Handbook. Sarajevo: South East European Youth Network. [Open Access] Retrieved from: https://www.salto-youth.net/downloads/toolbox_tool_download-file-1611/SEEYN%20LEADERSHIP%20HANDBOOK.pdf

Chapter 3 - How to solve Conflicts?

Sub-chapter 3.1 - Defining Conflict

¹ Kovač, H., Širol, M., & Šumanjski, M. (2017). Leadership Handbook. Sarajevo: South East European Youth Network. [Open Access] Retrieved from: https://www.salto-youth.net/downloads/toolbox_tool_download-file-1611/SEEYN%20LEADERSHIP%20HANDBOOK.pdf

² Tjosvold, D. (2006). Defining conflict and making choices about its management. *International Journal of Conflict Management*, 17(2), 87–95. doi:10.1108/10444060610736585

Sub-chapter 3.2 - Conflict Management

¹ Kovač, H., Širol, M., & Šumanjski, M. (2017). Leadership Handbook. Sarajevo: South East European Youth Network. Retrieved from: https://www.salto-youth.net/downloads/toolbox_tool_download-file-1611/SEEYN%20LEADERSHIP%20HANDBOOK.pdf

Sub-chapter 3.3 - Enabling Change after the Conflict

¹ Kovač, H., Širol, M., & Šumanjski, M. (2017). Leadership Handbook. Sarajevo: South East European Youth Network. [Open Access] Retrieved from: https://www.salto-youth.net/downloads/toolbox_tool_download-file-1611/SEEYN%20LEADERSHIP%20HANDBOOK.pdf

² Mitchell, C. R. (2011). Conflict, Change and Conflict resolution (p.75- p.100). In B. Austin, M. Fischer, H.J. Giessmann (eds.) 2011. Advancing Conflict Transformation. The Berghof Handbook II. Opladen/Framington Hills: Barbara Budrich Publishers. [Open Access] Retrieved from: <https://berghof-foundation.org/library>

Sub-chapter 3.4 - Tips to Improve your Skills

¹ Kovač, H., Širol, M., & Šumanjski, M. (2017). Leadership Handbook. Sarajevo: South East European Youth Network. [Open Access] Retrieved from: https://www.salto-youth.net/downloads/toolbox_tool_download-file-1611/SEEYN%20LEADERSHIP%20HANDBOOK.pdf

² Maslow, A. H. (1943). A theory of human motivation. *Psychological Review*, 50(4), 370–396. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0054346>

³ Manktelow, J., Brodbeck, F., & Ahow, N. (2016). How to Lead: Discover the Leader Within You. Mind Tools Ltd. [Open Access] Retrieved from: <https://www.mindtools.com/a43jjq5z/HowtoLead.pdf>

Chapter 4 - How important it is Motivation?

Sub-chapter 4.1 - Definition of Motivation

¹ Maslow, A. H. (1943). A theory of human motivation. *Psychological Review*, 50(4), 370–396. doi:doi.org/10.1037/h0054346

² Psychology Today. Motivation. [Open Access] Retrieved from: <https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/basics/motivation>

³ Kolzow, D. R. (2014). Leading from within: building organisational leadership capacity. [Open Access] Retrieved from: <https://pdf4pro.com/view/leading-from-within-building-organizational-leadership-46b3d1.html>

⁴ Manktelow, J., Brodbeck, F., & Ahow, N. (2016). How to Lead: Discover the Leader Within You. Mind Tools Ltd. [Open Access] Retrieved from: <https://www.mindtools.com/a43jjq5z/HowtoLead.pdf>

Sub-chapter 4.2 - Coaching

¹ Manktelow, J., Brodbeck, F., & Ahow, N. (2016). How to Lead: Discover the Leader Within You. Mind Tools Ltd. [Open Access] Retrieved from: <https://www.mindtools.com/a43jjq5z/HowtoLead.pdf>

² Fernández-Aráoz, C., Roscoe, A., & Aramaki, K. (2017). Turning potential into success: The missing link in leadership development. *Harvard Business Review*, 95(6), 86-93.

³ Kolzow, D. R. (2014). Leading from within: Building organisational leadership capacity. Retrieved from: <https://pdf4pro.com/view/leading-from-within-building-organizational-leadership-46b3d1.html>

⁴ Cairns, T. D., Hollenback, J., Preziosi, R. C., & Snow, W. A. (1998). Technical note: a study of Hersey and Blanchard's situational leadership theory. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 19(2), pp.113-116.doi:10.1108/01437739810208692

Sub-chapter 4.3 - Tips to Improve your Skills

¹ Kolzow, D. R. (2014). Leading from within: building organisational leadership capacity. [Open Access] Retrieved from: <https://pdf4pro.com/view/leading-from-within-building-organizational-leadership-46b3d1.html>

² Are you a Directive or a Supportive Leader? The Ken Blanchard Companies (2021). An SLII® eBook. [Open Access] Retrieved from: <https://www.blanchard.com.tr/Uploads/files/Arastirma/are-you-a-directive-or-supportive-leader.pdf>

Chapter 5 - Time Management

Sub-chapter 5.1 - How important is Time Management?

¹ Kovač, H., Širol, M., & Šumanjski, M. (2017). Leadership Handbook. Sarajevo: South East European Youth Network. [Open Access] Retrieved from: https://www.salto-youth.net/downloads/toolbox_tool_download-file-1611/SEEYN%20LEADERSHIP%20HANDBOOK.pdf

² Kate Dagher. Fellow. The Step-by-Step Guide on How to Prioritize Tasks (2020). [Open Access] Retrieved from: <https://fellow.app/blog/productivity/step-by-step-guide-on-how-to-prioritize-tasks/>

Sub-chapter 5.2 - Tips to Improve your Skills

¹ Kovač, H., Širol, M., & Šumanjski, M. (2017). Leadership Handbook. Sarajevo: South East European Youth Network. [Open Access] Retrieved from: https://www.salto-youth.net/downloads/toolbox_tool_download-file-1611/SEEYN%20LEADERSHIP%20HANDBOOK.pdf

² Kate Dagher. Fellow. The Step-by-Step Guide on How to Prioritize Tasks (2020). [Open Access] Retrieved from: <https://fellow.app/blog/productivity/step-by-step-guide-on-how-to-prioritize-tasks/>

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